

2025 IEEE PES ISGT Europe

October 20 - 23, 2025, Valletta, Malta

Impact of Uncontrolled Electric Vehicle Charging on Unbalanced Suburban Low-Voltage Networks

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Agenda

- Motivation
- Objectives
- Modeling and Analysis Framework
- Case Study & Datasets
- Results & Discussions
- Conclusions

Motivation

➤ The **rapid growth of EVs in residential areas** introduces **new operational challenges** in distribution grids, increasing the **urgency for infrastructure reinforcement** and planning.

➤ There is an increase interested in defining an **analysis framework and studies** to determine the **hosting capacity of uncontrolled EVs**, assessing how far existing low-voltage networks can accommodate them before technical limits are reached.

Objectives

- **Develop a Monte Carlo–based analysis framework** using *realistic, data-driven inputs*:
 - Smart-meter measurements
 - Local driving-behaviour surveys
 - Actual EV market statistics
 - Realistic DSO installation data for PVs and power supply types
- **Model three-phase unbalanced power flow** for a *real suburban low-voltage network* to capture realistic asymmetries
- **Quantify the combined impact** of *EV and PV penetration* on network loading, voltage deviation, and unbalance.

Modelling and Analysis Framework

Algorithm 1 MC-based analysis method

Require: Network data, household basic load profile, driving profile PDF, EV type data, EV charging infrastructure, PV generation profile.

```
for PV Pen.  $\in$  {20%, 40%, 60%} do
  for EV Pen.  $\in$  {0%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%} do
    for  $i \in$  {0, ..., 300} do  $\triangleright$  MC iterations
      • Random assign basic household load profiles
      • Basic load modification based on 3-day average substation measurements
      • Random assign individual EV profiles
      • Random assign individual PV profiles
      • Run quasi-dynamic simulation
    end for
  end for
end for
Present MC analysis results
```

Monte-Carlo Methodology

- 300 Monte Carlo iterations per EV–PV penetration scenario.
- 30-minute quasi-dynamic time resolution.
- Random spatial allocation of EVs, PVs, and household loads in each iteration.

Modelling and Analysis Framework

EV modeling (Driving data from survey and statistics)

Driving Patterns:

- Departure and arrival times
- Daily travel distance

Electric Vehicle Type (Based on European market data):

To translate driving behavior into charging demand, the model uses:

- Average energy consumption
- Battery capacity distribution

EV Charging Characteristics (IEC 62196-1):

- Four charging modes (from 3.7 kW AC up to 240 kW DC)
- Residential context:
 - 3-phase systems → 11 kW
 - 1-phase systems → 3.7 kW

ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND BATTERY CAPACITY OF THE 10 MOST POPULAR EV MODELS IN EUROPE FOR 2024.

Model	Energy Consumption (kWh/100km)	Range (km)	Sales (%)
Tesla Model Y	16.4	350	23.7
Tesla Model 3	13.7	420	20.7
MG 4	17.1	360	9.8
VW ID.3	16.4	360	9.6
Audi Q4 e-Tron	18.3	420	7.7
VW ID.4	17.3	445	7.0
VOLVO EX30	17.8	360	6.4
Skoda Enyaq	17.1	450	5.6
BMW iX1	17.0	380	5.1
Renault Megane	15.8	380	4.5
Average consumption:	16.7		

Modelling and Analysis Framework

LV Network, PV, and Household Load Modeling

Basic Household Load Profile (Smart Meter Data):

- Randomly assigned to each household using a uniform probability distribution.
- 218 real smart meter profiles from residential consumers.

PV Generation Profile (Statistical Data):

- Rooftop PV capacities assigned using statistical distributions provided by DSO.
- PV generation profile identical in per-unit terms (due to geographic proximity) but scaled according to installed capacity.

LV Distribution Network (Pandapower Modeling):

- Realistic suburban network with **three radial feeders**.
- **Unbalanced three-phase** configuration.
- **11/0.4 kV, 315 kVA Δ -Y transformer**.
- **61 nodes** serving **84 residential customers** (max. 3 per node).

Key Findings (1)

Average load profile

- EV charging mainly occurs during **evening peak hours**, intensifying overall demand.
- At **high penetration levels**, EV demand becomes comparable to the base residential load — **nearly doubling** total network consumption during peaks.

Transformer Loading

- The stress period is limited between **15:00-20:00**
- Each **+20% EV** penetration increases transformer loading by about **25%**, reaching in the worst case up to **160% at 80% EVs**.
- PV integration provides only slight relief and has **no impact before 10:00 and after 18:00**

Key Findings (2)

Line Loading

- Line loading increases by **10–13%** for every **+20% EV penetration**.
- **PVs have negligible effect** on the line stress.
- No line overloads occur, but **thermal margins gradually decrease**.

Voltage Deviation

- Average voltage **drops by ~ 0.01 p.u.** for every **+20% increase in EV penetration**.
- **Voltage limit violations** appear at **60% and 80%** EV penetration levels.
- **PV generation has a negligible impact** on minimum voltage levels during peak evening.

Voltage Unbalance Factor (IEC 61000)

- **VUF increases slightly ($\sim 0.2\%$)** for every **+20% EV penetration**.
- The impact remains **insignificant**, as most suburban chargers are **three-phase**.

Conclusions & Contributions

➤ This study advances previous works by improving the **realism** of EV–PV integration analysis using real data and unbalanced power flow modeling.

➤ Key Takeaways:

- **Transformer overloading** is the dominant constraint for uncontrolled EV integration in suburban LV networks.
- **Voltage violations (<0.9 p.u.)** appear from **≥60% EV penetration**.
- **PV generation** cannot mitigate evening peak impacts.
- **Distribution lines** stay within safe limits but operate **closer to capacity** as EV levels rise.
- **VUF** remains **within IEC limits (~2%)** under all scenarios.

➤ Future Work:

- **Integrate additional energy systems** (e.g., heating and cooling) into a **multi-energy framework** and develop **realistic operational strategies** to **optimally coordinate** these multi-disciplinary systems.

Acknowledgments & Contact

- This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the GA n. 101120278 - DENSE.

Thank you

"together, we move toward a more sustainable energy future."

2025 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe (ISGT-Europe)
October 20-23, 2025, Valletta, Malta